

METROLOGY
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Good practice guide

Use of the transfer standard light source developed for the
visible spectral range

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes the design, specifications, operating conditions, and limitations of the developed sources for the visible spectral range between 360 nm and 830 nm.

2. Definitions

Dissemination of the unit of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the unit of the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux, Φ_e , with respect to area, A , at a point on a real or imaginary surface, $E_e = d\Phi_e/dA$. The irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}$ (see 17-21-053 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Measurement standard: Realization of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see 5.1 in [JCGM 200:2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (see 5.4 in [JCGM 200:2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Realization of the unit of the (spectral) irradiance: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Spectral irradiance: Density of the irradiance, $E_e(\lambda)$ with respect to wavelength, λ , $E_{e,\lambda} = dE_e(\lambda)/d\lambda$. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W\ m^{-2}\ nm^{-1}$ (see 17-21-056 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

Visible (VIS) radiation: optical radiation capable of causing a visual sensation directly.

There are no precise limits for the spectral range of visible radiation since they depend upon the amount of radiant flux reaching the retina and the responsivity of the observer. The lower limit is generally taken between 360 nm and 400 nm and the upper limit between 760 nm and 830 nm. (see 17-21-003 in [CIE S 017:2020]).

In this document we define the lower VIS limit to 360 nm and the upper VIS limit to 830 nm to cover any existing wavelength range definitions.

3. General requirements and preliminary considerations

3.1. Spectral distribution of the transfer standard

The uncertainty contributions arising from the spectrometer's wavelength scale uncertainty become particularly significant when steep spectral slopes are present, such as at the edges of LED emission peaks. In these regions, even a small wavelength error or wavelength uncertainty cause a disproportionately large change in the measured spectral irradiance, thereby dominating the total measurement uncertainty. To minimize this effect, it is advisable to design or select light sources whose spectral distributions avoid sharp transitions or peak structures whenever possible. A smoother spectrum reduces the effect of wavelength calibration errors and improves the reliability and reproducibility of the measurement results.

Figure 1 – RGB LED: It is clearly recognisable that a small shift in the wavelength leads to a considerable change in the spectral irradiance at the edges of the LED peaks.

Taking the measurement uncertainty into account, the ideal spectrum is therefore one in which the spectral irradiance is constant over the entire visible wavelength range. This distribution is called CIE illuminant E. CIE illuminant E is a purely hypothetical, idealised light source that has equal energy at each wavelength in the visible spectrum. It does not correspond to any natural or common artificial light, but is used as a mathematical and conceptual reference in colorimetry.

Figure 2 – Illuminant E. It is not a blackbody and therefore does not have a true colour temperature, but its chromaticity can be approximated by a daylight-type illuminant with a correlated colour temperature of about 5455 K.

Illuminant E is a hypothetical, non-existent spectrum that cannot be perfectly realised in practice. Therefore, calibrated light sources with this spectrum are not available. The spectrum of the new reference light source should nevertheless be adapted as closely as possible to the CIE E distribution.

3.2. Selection of LEDs – Approach A

A total of 35 different LED types from various manufacturers were identified as suitable based on a market survey and subsequently purchased. In total, 120 LEDs were operated on a temperature-stabilized heatsink on the surface of a 1.65-meter integrating sphere equipped with a spectrometer for approximately 1000 hours.

This experimental setup enables consistent measurement conditions and long-term performance testing of the LEDs, ensuring stable temperature and precise spectral characterization throughout the duration of the test.

Figure 3 shows the rear of the active temperature-controlled LED board mounted on the side port of an integrating sphere. There are 120 relays for selectively switching on and off single or multiple LEDs.

Figure 3 – Temperature controlled LED-Board

Figure 4 shows an overview of the integrating sphere used during the first operating test of the LEDs.

- **Figure 4 – Image of the opened integrating sphere during the first operational test. The lamp holder rod was of course removed during the seasoning tests.**

The LEDs are operated simultaneously for seasoning. Spectral measurements were taken regularly during the seasoning process. In addition, the LEDs are operated and measured individually from time to time. This was done approximately every 100 hours.

Figure 5 – Close-up of the 120 LEDs on the inside of the sphere

In the end, 28 LED types were identified as suitable based on their long-term aging behavior, meaning they showed stable output and only limited degradation over the test period. Each of these LEDs was then characterized individually to obtain its precise spectral power distribution. Using these measured spectra, a composite spectrum was numerically simulated by combining the contributions of the selected LEDs so that the resulting distribution covers the entire visible range and is as close as possible to an equal-energy (near flat) spectrum. This synthesized spectrum can serve as a tailored broadband illuminant for applications that require uniform spectral coverage, such as spectroradiometer calibration.

Figure 6 – Simulated spectrum (rainbow-coloured) from the combination of the measured individual spectra of the LEDs (white spectra).

There are still individual peaks, but with a maximum variation of $\pm 20\%$, which seems acceptable. The individual LED types and the associated operating currents for achieving an energy spectrum are listed below.

Table 1 – Overview of LEDs that have proven to be suitable after seasoning and characterisation.

Number	Peak Wavelength or CCT	LED Type	Current /A	Relative Current
1	365nm	SMB1N-365V	0.361	100%
2	4000K	SCP9TTF1HEL1TUH34E	0.341	95%
3	770nm	SMB1N-770	0.309	86%
4	727nm	GF CSSPM1.24-2T4T-1	0.277	77%

5	850nm	SFH 4716AS	0.273	76%
6	405nm	15335340AA350	0.272	75%
7	800nm	SMB1N-800D	0.265	73%
8	470nm	GB QSSPA1.13-HYJX-35-1	0.221	61%
9	385nm	SMB1N-385V	0.220	61%
10	430nm	SMB1N-430H	0.217	60%
11	395nm	SMB1N-395V	0.212	59%
12	830nm	SMB1N-830N	0.198	55%
13	700nm	SMB1N-700D	0.192	53%
14	375nm	SMB1N-375V	0.139	39%
15	750nm	SMB1N-750D	0.128	36%
16	490nm	SMB1N-490H	0.113	31%
17	680nm	SMB1N-680D	0.107	30%
18	515nm	SMB1N-515V	0.060	17%
19	657nm	GH CSSRM4.24-V7V9-1-1-700-R33	0.048	13%
20	830nm	SMB1N-830N	0.040	11%
21	448nm	GD CSSRML.14-U9V2-24-1-350-R33	0.038	11%
22	550nm	SMB1N-550H	0.027	7%
23	593nm	GY CSHPM1.23-KPKR-36	0.025	7%
24	568nm	LXML-PX02-0000	0.019	5%
25	385nm	SMB1N-385V	0.009	2%
26	528nm	GT QSSPA1.13-LSLU-26-1	0.003	1%
27	570nm	SMC570	0.003	1%
28	505nm	LV CRBP.01-KXLY-AD-Q525-350-R18	0.002	0.5%

To achieve an approximately equal-energy spectrum, the drive currents of the individual LEDs had to be adjusted over a very wide range, which made the system inherently complex and sensitive. Attempts to balance the optical output by arranging LEDs in parallel groups and using series resistors to trim the flux of each device were only partially successful. Even small changes in the temperature led to noticeable shifts in the relative output of the individual LEDs, because their forward voltage and efficiency are strongly temperature dependent.

Grouping several LEDs and operating them in series reduced the number of channels somewhat, but even in this configuration at least ten independent current drivers were still required. Such a large number of separate, precisely controlled current supplies is not useful for a transfer standard light source, as it increases cost, complexity, and the risk of drift or mismatch between channels. In practice, this architecture would require continuous monitoring and frequent recalibration to maintain the expected uncertainties of the target spectrum, which contradicts the goal of a simple, robust, and reproducible reference source.

Fortunately, a new type of LED came onto the market during the characterisation process that proved to be more suitable. This approach was therefore discontinued at this point and the other LED type is described in the following chapter.

3.3. Selection of LEDs – Approach B

Due to the previously described issue of needing at least ten separate current drivers, another market survey for alternative LEDs was conducted. In this search, a new product line from Yujileds was identified that appeared particularly promising. These LEDs combine several pump LEDs with different wavelength-converting phosphors in a single package to generate a broadband spectral power distribution. The manufacturer even advertises a spectrum that closely resembles the hypothetical CIE illuminant E, i.e., with a very smooth, nearly equal-energy distribution across the visible range.

Figure 7 – Screenshot of Yujileds advertisement

Such integrated broadband LEDs are attractive for calibration purposes because they can provide wide spectral coverage with only one or a few current channels instead of many individually driven monochromatic LEDs. This significantly reduces system complexity, wiring effort, and the risk of spectral instability due to mismatched or drifting current sources, making the realization of a practical calibration light source much more feasible.

According to the data sheet, a single LED provides an optical output of approximately 3.6 W when driven at 18 V and 200 mA. To achieve a sufficiently high irradiance at a distance of about 700 mm on the entrance optics of a spectroradiometer, ten of these LEDs are driven in series. In this configuration, the same current flows through all the devices, so the total optical power is approximately the sum of the individual contributions, while the required supply voltage increases accordingly. Operating multiple LEDs in series on a thermally stabilised heatsink helps to maintain uniform operating conditions and reduces current balancing problems, which is important for achieving stable and reproducible irradiance at the measurement plane of the spectroradiometer being calibrated.

Figure 8 shows an overview measurement of 10 LEDs in a distance of 700mm

Figure 8 – PTB Measurement of 10 Yujiled LEDs @ 700mm Distance

As can be seen in Figure 8, the spectral irradiance above 400nm is sufficiently high and also quite constant over the wavelength range. In particular, the phosphor-converted part of the emission spectrum shows almost no narrowband peaks, indicating a homogeneous and broadband output in the visible. However,

below 400nm the irradiance is too low to be useful for the requested calibration or measurement applications. Fortunately, suitable LEDs were available from the earlier Approach A to fill these short wavelength gaps. By carefully combining the phosphor-converted broadband LEDs with these additional UV or violet LEDs, it was possible to achieve a more continuous and sufficiently intense spectrum through the entire visible range. This hybrid approach exploits the smoothness and stability of the phosphor-converted LEDs in the visible range, while supplementing the spectrum where their output is weak, enabling the construction of a calibration source that closely meets the requirements for uniform spectral coverage and high total irradiance.

Figure 9 – Combination of 5 UV-LEDs and 10 Yujiled LEDs @ 700mm

Figure 9 shows the combined spectrum of the ten Yujiled LEDs together with additional UV LEDs with peak wavelengths between 365 and 405 nm. In this configuration, the basic requirements for a continuous visible spectrum with sufficiently high irradiance are met, and the overall spectral power distribution appears smooth and free of pronounced narrowband artefacts over most of the VIS range.

Prior to further optimisation or fine tuning of the spectral shape, emphasis was placed on evaluating the temporal stability of this LED combination over operating time. For use as a calibration light source, not only the instantaneous spectral distribution but also its long-term stability is critical. Systematic seasoning tests were therefore planned to quantify how both total radiant flux and spectral shape evolve during prolonged operation, and to verify that any changes remain within acceptable tolerance limits for high precision spectroradiometer calibration.

3.4. Seasoning

LEDs should be seasoned (pre-aged) before being used as reference lamps because their aging process affects performance stability over time. Initially, LEDs experience more significant changes in radiant flux, color characteristics, and efficiency due to various degradation mechanisms including phosphor conversion efficiency decline and thermal effects. With increasing operating time, the rate of aging slows down, leading to a more stable output, which is crucial when LEDs are used as calibration or reference light sources. Seasoning helps to ensure that the LED's output has settled into a stable phase where temporal changes are minimal, improving measurement reliability and reducing uncertainty caused by ongoing aging effects during use. This time-dependent behavior means the LED's light output and spectral properties are more consistent after initial aging, making it better suited as a reference

Figure 10 – relative change of irradiance (not spectral irradiance) over 294 hours

Figure 10 shows the change in irradiance over the full range of wavelengths emitted by the LED source over time. After an initial run-in period of about 150 hours, the signal follows a very well linear decrease that can be described mathematically with high accuracy. The observed drift is significantly less than 10^{-5} per hour, so the irradiance remains after mathematical correction effectively constant for most practical measurement times.

Such a small, predictable aging rate is highly advantageous for establishing a transfer standard, as the temporal behaviour can be reliably modelled and, if necessary, corrected in the calibration procedure. This means that calibration laboratories can use the source to transfer spectral irradiance scales between instruments or facilities while maintaining traceability and quantifiable uncertainty contributions from source ageing.

Figure 11 – Seasoning behaviour over 294 hours. A spectrum was measured every 2 hours.

Figure 11 shows the spectrally resolved seasoning behaviour of the LED source over a total operating time of 294 hours. For this experiment, one spectrum was recorded every two hours, and all 147 spectra were plotted on top of each other to visualize how the spectral irradiance evolves over time across the full wavelength range.

In the subsequent plot, the relative change of each spectrum with respect to the final measurement is shown. The blue curve corresponds to the first recorded spectrum and indicates that the signal around 500 nm was roughly 4% higher compared to the end of the test. Toward longer operating times, the individual curves lie increasingly close together, clearly illustrating that the rate of change diminishes with time and the system gradually approaches a quasi-steady state, which is advantageous for establishing a stable calibration source.

Rel. changes of the Spectral Irradiance @ 700mm /W/nm/m²

Figure 12 – Spectral changes over 294 hours. A spectrum was measured every 2 hours. The diagram shows the relative changes compared to the last measured spectrum.

Figure 13 shows only the last 20 measurements taken over the last 40 hours of operation. Over most of the wavelength range, the relative changes in spectral irradiance are negligible, indicating that the source has largely reached a steady state.

Rel. changes of the Spectral Irradiance @ 700mm /W/nm/m²

Figure 13 – Spectral changes over 40 hours. A spectrum was measured every 2 hours. The diagram shows the relative changes compared to the last measured spectrum

As expected, the largest variations occur at the 365 nm UV LEDs with the highest photon energy, and there is a distinct residual peak around 500 nm where small drift is still visible. Nevertheless, the corresponding rates of change per hour—below about $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 495 nm and $1.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at 360 nm—remain well within an acceptable range for high-precision applications. Overall, this behavior demonstrates that the LED combination is sufficiently stable to serve as the basis for a spectral irradiance transfer standard.

3.5. Short term instability of the transfer standard

The activity report A1.2.2 investigates experimentally how short-term instabilities in LED light sources, used as transfer standards, influence the calibration of spectroradiometers concerning irradiance measurements. It specifically analyzes how integration time, periodic fluctuations in irradiance, and the spectroradiometer's own noise impact measurement accuracy. The methodology involved modulating an LED-based light source with a controllable power supply to produce periodic irradiance variations at different amplitudes and periods.

A photodiode monitored these variations every 0.1 seconds, while the actual measurements were performed with a spectroradiometer, which used various integration times, simulated by adjusting distance.

The results showed that irradiance variations caused by modulation could be kept below 0.01%, with the spectroradiometer noise dominating measurement errors when fluctuations stayed under this threshold. Longer integration times and lower modulation frequencies increased the signal-to-noise ratio, and a high correlation was observed across different wavelengths, indicating that the dominant noise affected all spectral regions similarly. Spectral integration did not reduce this noise further. Theoretical analysis supported that the relative standard deviation of the spectral response depended on the ratio between the integration time and the modulation period.

The key conclusion was that short-term fluctuations in the light source below 0.01% do not significantly distort calibration results. Instead, the primary influence comes from the spectroradiometer's own noise and the precision of the integration time measurement. These findings are particularly relevant for laboratories employing LED-based transfer standards, providing guidance for selecting optimal measurement parameters and understanding the limits of light source stability's effect on measurement accuracy.

Since the fluctuations in the irradiance of an LED light source are strongly correlated with the fluctuations of its power supply current, the noise in the current source can be considered a proportional factor influencing the noise of the light source. In other words, variations in the electrical current directly translate to proportional variations in the light output, meaning that any instability or noise in the driving current inherently causes corresponding fluctuations in the LED's emitted light intensity.

Therefore, it is most important to ensure that the power supply feeding the LED has a high level of stability, ideally better than 0.01%, to minimize noise and fluctuations in light output. Maintaining such strict current stability is essential to achieve accurate and reliable measurements, as even small current deviations can significantly affect the LED's emitted light intensity. This emphasizes the need to use high-quality, stable current sources or LED drivers in precision applications.

The Keithley 2460 SourceMeter has a current stability specification that typically is better than 0.1% under normal conditions. Specifically, for the 200 mA range, it offers very precise current sourcing with stability and accuracy including line and load regulation on the order of 0.01% of range plus very small incremental errors. This means the current supplied at 200 mA is stable with fluctuations well below 0.1%, and often close to or under 0.01% depending on the specific measurement setup and conditions. This makes the Keithley 2460 highly suitable for operating the transfer standard for precision calibrations.

The entire report can be found in Appendix A1.

3.6. Temperature stabilisation

LEDs should be operated on a temperature-stabilized heatsink when used as references because temperature significantly impacts their optical parameters.

The emitted flux and spectral characteristics of LEDs vary with temperature, typically decreasing optical power as temperature rises due to mechanisms such as non-radiative recombination and carrier leakage.

Stabilizing the temperature ensures more consistent light output and colour stability, which is crucial for reliable measurements and calibration. Without temperature control, variations of ambient temperature affect the thermal equilibrium and lead to fluctuations in light output and peak wavelengths, reducing the stability and accuracy of the LED as a reference source.

Using a temperature-stabilized heatsink minimizes these temperature-induced variations, enhancing the precision and repeatability of optical referencing with LEDs. The used Sourcemeters and the temperature stabilisation should be connected to the mains for at least 2 hours. The LEDs of the LIS-A² light source can then be switched on and measurements can be taken after a warm-up time of around 5 minutes.

Figure 14 – This is a separate enclosure designed to interface with the LIS-A² light source. On the front panel, there are connectors for powering three independent LED circuits, each labeled with its respective current and voltage ratings. A toggle switch activates the built-in alignment laser. A green indicator LED in the right image shows that the source has reached thermal equilibrium.

3.7. Design description

The design of the LIS-A light source from the EURAMET European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project 15SIB07 PhotoLED (<http://photoled.aalto.fi/>) was successful and serves as the basis for the development of a broadband VIS source.

Figure 15 – LIS-A reference light source

The housing includes high-quality temperature stabilisation and a proven and good arrangement of individual LEDs. As the new source requires several different LED types to be operated at different currents, the housing and circuit design have been adapted. In addition, a laser was built into the housing to align the source, which shines through the LED board and specifies the direction in which the coupling optics of the spectroradiometer should be attached.

The result is a source which we call LIS-A² and which is shown and described in the following images.

Figure 16 – The left rendered image shows the LIS-A² source. The marked laser beam indicates the measurement direction. The right image shows the real prototype during the NEWSTAND measurement campaign at the PTB.

Figure 17 – Front view of the LIS-A² with dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 18 – Side view of the LIS-A² with dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 19 – Bottom side view. An optical post or tripod can be attached to the bottom of the LIS-A² standard light source. There is one M6 tapped hole and one 1/4" tapped hole at the base. There are two additional bores with H7 tolerance. The bottom side should be aligned perpendicular to gravity.

3.8. Transfer standard light source: LIS-A²

For the measurement campaign at PTB and for comparison measurements between different laboratories, three LIS-A² standard lamps were built.

Figure 20 – Three LIS-A² artifacts with and without protective caps

The images in Figure 20 show three LIS-A² standard lamps arranged vertically. In the left panel, each lamp is fitted with a protective cap covering the emission aperture to shield the front glass and LED array and prevent contamination or mechanical damage during storage and transport. In the right panel, these caps have been removed, revealing the circular LED boards with the ring of broadband Yujileds and the central UV LEDs inside each housing. The consistent mechanical design and interchangeable front caps support reproducible positioning and handling in calibration setups, while the robust enclosures provide thermal and mechanical stability for the light sources.

Figure 21 – LED arrangement and central LASER beam for alignment

Each lamp contains an LED board with ten Yujiled CIE-E LEDs arranged in a circular ring and an additional set of five UV LEDs with peak wavelengths of 365 nm, 375 nm, 385 nm, 395 nm, and 405 nm mounted inside the ring.

Figure 22 – Full LIS-A² setup

Figure 22 shows a single standard LIS-A² lamp and its associated power sources. The LIS-A² is mounted on an adjustable post on the optical table, while three stacked SourceMeter units on the right provide precisely controlled currents for the different LED strings. The LED drive currents are set to very low levels to avoid saturating the camera image, so that the individual emitters are clearly visible. The inner ring of the LED array shows the different coloured UV LEDs, surrounded by the brighter broadband Yujileds which form the outer ring and dominate the visible output.

Every board is divided into three independent current circuits. Since connecting all ten broadband LEDs in series would require an impractically high supply voltage of about 180 V, they are split into two separate strings of five identical LEDs, each operated at 200 mA. A third circuit supplies the five UV LEDs. The drive current of the UV channel is adjusted so that, in combination with the broadband Yujileds, the resulting composite spectrum exhibits an almost constant spectral irradiance over the entire visible range as shown in Figure 23. This electrical architecture allows precise, reproducible control of the spectral power distribution while keeping the operating voltages within a safe and convenient range.

Figure 23 – Relative spectral irradiance of a LIS-A² artifact

Because the UV LEDs inside the LIS-A could not be arranged in a perfectly rotationally symmetric pattern, the irradiance uniformity had to be verified at different distances from the source. The following figures show the relative spectral irradiance over the wavelength range from 340 nm to 800 nm for two distances. The blue circle marks a field with a diameter of 11.3 mm, corresponding to the typical entrance optics of spectroradiometers according to CIE report 127:2007 (Measurement of LEDs), while the black circle indicates a 20 mm diameter, which covers the vast majority of practical detector apertures. Since typical measurement distances lie between 350 mm and 700 mm, the irradiance distribution was characterized for both distances. In both cases, the color maps demonstrate that within the blue and black circles the relative deviations from the central irradiance level are very small, indicating a highly uniform illumination of the detector aperture. For intermediate distances, which will be used in real measurement setups, the field can be expected to be at least as uniform, so the LIS-A² geometry is well suited for accurate spectroradiometer calibration without introducing significant spatial nonuniformity errors.

Figure 24 – VIS irradiance uniformity at a distance of 350 mm

Figure 25 – VIS irradiance uniformity at a distance of 700 mm

3.9. Safety and handling instructions

To prevent the source from damage, the following handling instructions must be respected:

- **Avoid looking directly into the illuminated aperture, especially at close distances, as the intense visible and UV radiation may cause eye strain or damage!**
- Use appropriate eye protection when working near the lamp without beam enclosures.
- Ensure that all personnel working with the LIS-A² are trained in its operation and familiar with general LED and UV safety guidelines, including applicable photobiological safety standards.
- The source is meant for operation in laboratory conditions and should not be used in other environments.
- Operate the LIS-A² lamp only with the specified power supplies and wiring; do not modify the electrical connections or exceed the rated currents and voltages.
- Ensure that the protective front cap is mounted whenever the lamp is not in use or is being transported, to prevent mechanical damage and contamination of the optics.
- Allow sufficient ventilation around the housing and do not cover cooling openings; operate the lamp only within the specified ambient temperature range between +10°C and 30°C.
- Switch off the lamp and disconnect it from the power supplies before moving, performing any mechanical adjustments, cleaning, or reconfiguration of the setup.
- Current to the LEDs must not be applied when the TEC is inactive.
- No reverse bias should be applied to the LEDs.
- The source must not be exposed to liquids, moisture, dust or flames. Use only dry, lint-free materials and suitable cleaning agents for the front window; never use aggressive solvents on optical or plastic parts.

The following procedure is recommended to operate the LIS-A² standard light source.

1. Use an M6 or 1/4" optical post to hold the LIS-A² standard light source and align the bottom perpendicular to gravity.
2. Connect all cables, and plug the TEC and Sourcemeters to the mains and switch them on. **Do not activate the power output of the sourcemeters, yet.**
3. Remove the dust protection cap.
4. Align the LIS-A² standard light source. You can use cameras, the internal laser or other devices to do this.
5. Wait at least 2 hours to allow the instruments to warm so that their internal temperature reaches equilibrium. Do not operate the LEDs during this warm-up period. After the warm-up time, the SourceMeters can be assumed to meet their specified accuracy and stability, and you may then enable the outputs and start driving the LEDs.
6. Wait at least until the status LED on the separate enclosure switches on (Figure 14). We recommend waiting for 10 minutes warm-up time to achieve a highly stable thermal equilibrium.
7. Carry out your measurements.
8. Turn off the LEDs.
9. Put the dust protection cap on the LIS-A² standard light source.

3.10. Advantages and disadvantages

In comparison to a quartz halogen lamp, the main drawback of the LIS-A² LED source is the presence of individual peaks in the spectral distribution rather than a perfectly smooth continuum. In addition, the system requires a temperature controller and several separate current drivers, which increases complexity and cost.

However, during operation the temporal aging of the LEDs is significantly smaller than that of a halogen lamp, so the output remains more stable over long measurement campaigns. The source also exhibits lower intensity noise, and the spectral irradiance between 400 nm and 800 nm is nearly constant, which is advantageous for spectroradiometric calibration.

The most important advantage is the absence of out-of-range stray light. A halogen lamp emits a very large fraction of its power in the infrared, and this strong IR component can generate considerable internal stray light in the blue region of VIS spectroradiometers, thereby degrading measurement accuracy. In contrast, the LIS-A² spectrum is much more similar to common practical light sources used in applications, with minimal emission outside the relevant spectral range, so this reduction in stray light and improved representativeness of real-world illumination conditions is the dominant benefit (substitution method).

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

Activity report

Version Date: 22 May 2024

Task 1.2 Development of broadband transfer standard light sources

A1.2.2 (Partial activity by CSIC in collaboration with PTB) Evaluation of the impact of the light source short-term instability on the calibration in irradiance of spectroradiometer.

Start date: 01 December 2023

Duration: 17 months

Involved partners:
PTB, CSIC, GOO, NPL

1. Introduction

The objective of this work, carried out at the *Instituto de Óptica* in CSIC, is to evaluate the impact of the short-term instability of the light sources developed as transfer standard in the result of the calibration in irradiance of spectroradiometers. This impact depends on the integration time of specific measurements, and on the own read out noise of the test spectroradiometer. We evaluated this experimentally by producing periodic variations of the irradiance on the spectroradiometer with different amplitudes, for different integration times. This periodic variation of the irradiance was produced by controlling the current of the light source.

2. Methodology

CSIC received a LED-based light source (LIS-A) from PTB, whose design is the proposed for the transfer light source in the visible, and a programmable sourcemeter (Model 2460 High-Current Interactive SourceMeter Instrument, Keithley).

The sourcemeter was PC-controlled by Matlab, in order to change dynamically the supply current to LIS-A.

The supply current was limited to a maximum of $I_{\max} = 65$ mA (limit of voltage of 71.3 V), and modified according to the expression:

$$I = I_{\max} \frac{[1 - A \cos(2\pi t/P)]}{(1 + A)} \quad (1)$$

Where t is the time, P the period of variation, and A is an amplitude that allows the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (σ_r) to be modified by selecting $A = 3\sigma_r/2$, as tested experimentally.

In order to monitor the irradiance value, a Hamamatsu Si photodiode (together with a Keithley 6485 picoammeter) was used in front of LIS-A to acquire a value for each change in the supply current. The current is changed every 0.1 s using Eq. (1), and after that the photodiode acquires a value of the photocurrent. When the acquisition is finished a new value of the supply current is set, based on the internal clock of the computer.

Periods, P , of 0 s, 1 s, 2 s, 4 s and 8 s and relative standard deviations, σ_r , of 0.01, 0.001 and 0.0001 were selected for this study. Periods lower than 1 s did not allow a proper sampling on the irradiance variation (it was limited by the monitoring process), whereas we did not see much difference between result with $\sigma_r = 0.0001$ and lower values for this parameter.

Once the correct realization of the periodic variation was verified, the variation of the signal of a spectroradiometer Konica Minolta CS-1000 was tested under the mentioned (P , σ_r) configurations of irradiance. The monitoring of the irradiance with the photodiode was used during this evaluation, by displacing the photodiode to avoid the occlusion of LIS-A from the spectroradiometer. The spectroradiometer was controlled in a parallel session so that it not interferes with the realization of the irradiance modulation. The spectroradiometer takes some time in acquiring a single spectrum (no less than 15 s), because it evaluates first the proper integration time for each level of irradiance. 30 acquisitions were used to evaluate the impact of the short-term instability of the light source (between 8 min and 11 min). In order to evaluate the response at different integration times, we modified the irradiance on the spectroradiometer by modifying the distance. Three distances were selected allowing integration times, t_{int} , of 1.5 s, 3 s and 5.6 s.

A picture of the setup is shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Picture of the setup.

3. Results

The results of the relative variation of the irradiance produced by LIS-A under the different (P, σ_r) configurations is shown Figure 27. In addition, in the figure is included the period of 5 s, to show the effect of undersampling the variation of irradiance, and $\sigma_r = 0.00005$, showing that it is possible to achieve such small variation with this method.

Figure 27: Variation of the irradiance produced by LIS-A under the different (P , σ_t) configurations.

In Figure 28, it is shown the relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current. The coefficient of sensitivity is 14.7 A^{-1} , calculated as the slope of the data represented in the figure.

Figure 28: Relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current.

An example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer is shown in Figure 29, for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P , σ_t) configurations. Note the effect of undersampling in the variation of the response of the spectroradiometer, which makes that the observed period is longer than the period of the irradiance. A wavelength of 580 nm was selected for the results presented in Figure 29, in the fluorescent emission. The analogue figure for the wavelength at 450 nm (blue peak of the emission) is shown in Figure 30. No important differences between both figures are observed. The same plots are represented for spectrally integrated data between 470 nm and 700 nm, and shown in Figure 31.

Figure 29: [Data for 580 nm] Example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P, σ_r) configurations.

Figure 30: [Data for 450 nm] Example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P , σ_r) configurations.

Figure 31: [Spectrally integrated data between 470 nm and 700 nm] Example of the relative variation of the response of the spectroradiometer for an integration time of 1.5 s, under the different (P , σ_r) configurations.

The summary of the results is provided in Table 2, where the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (from photodiode) and of the spectroradiometer response (for 580 nm and the spectrally integrated value between 470 nm and 700 nm) are presented for the different configurations and integration times. The results for 580 nm are shown as a plot in Figure 32, where the relative standard deviation of the responses is represented as a function of the ratio between the period of the irradiance and the integration time used by the spectroradiometer. The relevance of expressing this variation according to this independent variable is supported by the theoretical development explained in the “Discussion and conclusions” section, in Eq. (8).

In order to identify any difference among wavelengths, the relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer, for no modulated irradiance, is shown in Figure 33. The variation in the relative standard deviations at different wavelength is mostly due the different magnitude of irradiance (the relative standard deviation due exclusively to the photon noise decreases inversely proportional the square of the irradiance).

Table 2. Summary table for the LIS-A light source with the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (from photodiode) and of the spectroradiometer response, for the different configurations and integration times.

Integration time / s	Period / s	Standard deviation of the irradiance	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (580 nm)	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (470 nm – 700 nm)
1,5	0	0,001%	0,015%	0,01%
	1	0,011%	0,010%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,02%
		0,98%	0,15%	0,15%
	2	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,03%
		0,98%	0,26%	0,26%
	4	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,08%	0,08%
		0,98%	0,77%	0,77%
	8	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,09%	0,09%
0,98%		0,95%	0,94%	
3,0	0	0,003%	0,021%	0,021%
	1	0,011%	0,014%	0,011%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,01%
		0,98%	0,02%	0,02%
	2	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,03%	0,02%
		0,98%	0,27%	0,27%
	4	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,04%	0,03%
		0,98%	0,42%	0,42%
	8	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,08%	0,08%
0,98%		0,81%	0,80%	
5,6	0	0,002%	0,012%	0,012%
	1	0,011%	0,015%	0,011%
		0,10%	0,01%	0,02%
		0,99%	0,08%	0,11%
	2	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,98%	0,06%	0,08%
	4	0,01%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,02%	0,01%
		0,98%	0,04%	0,04%
	8	0,01%	0,01%	0,01%
		0,10%	0,02%	0,01%
0,98%		0,05%	0,04%	

Figure 32: (LIS-A) Relative standard deviation of the responses is represented as a function of the ratio between the period of the irradiance and the integration time used by the spectroradiometer (580 nm).

Figure 33: (Top) Normalized spectral power distribution (SPD) of the spectral irradiance of LIS-A. (Bottom) Relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer, for no modulated irradiance.

In order to rule out a possible dependence on the light source in this analysis, the same methodology was followed for NICHIA NLSW30S01A. In this case, a Peltier controller was used to keep the Platinum RTD temperature at 90°C. The supply current was limited to a maximum of $I_{max} = 200$ mA (limit of voltage of 47.5 V).

In Figure 28, it is shown the relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current. The coefficient of sensitivity is 7.77 A^{-1} , calculated as the slope of the data represented in the figure.

In this case, periods, P , of 0 s, 1 s, 2 s, 4 s and 8 s and relative standard deviations, σ_r , of 0.001 and 0.0001 were selected, at two integration times 2.5 s and 5.5 s. The results for NICHIA are shown in Table 3, and Figure 35 and Figure 36.

Figure 34: Relative variation of the irradiance with respect to the supply current, for the Nichia light source.

Table 3. Summary table for the NICHA light source with the relative standard deviation of the irradiance (from photodiode) and of the spectroradiometer response, for the different configurations and integration times.

Integration time / s	Period / s	Standard deviation of the irradiance	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (650 nm)	Standard deviation of the spectroradiometer response (393 nm – 700 nm)	
2,5	0	0,006%	0,014%	0,014%	
	1	0,014%	0,015%	0,005%	
		0,11%	0,02%	0,01%	
	2	0,01%	0,02%	0,008%	
		0,11%	0,03%	0,02%	
	4	0,01%	0,02%	0,006%	
		0,11%	0,05%	0,05%	
	8	0,02%	0,03%	0,02%	
		0,11%	0,09%	0,10%	
	5,5	0	0,01%	0,022%	0,022%
		1	0,01%	0,027%	0,009%
			0,11%	0,04%	0,01%
2		0,01%	0,02%	0,008%	
		0,112%	0,045%	0,013%	
4		0,014%	0,023%	0,008%	
		0,11%	0,04%	0,03%	
8		0,01%	0,04%	0,009%	
		0,11%	0,06%	0,06%	

Figure 35: (NICHIA) Relative standard deviation of the responses is represented as a function of the ratio between the period of the irradiance and the integration time used by the spectroradiometer (650 nm).

Figure 36: (Top) Normalized spectral power distribution (SPD) of the spectral irradiance of LIS-A. (Bottom) Relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer, for no modulated irradiance.

4. Discussion and conclusions

There are some conclusions that can be drawn from Table 2.

For a period of 0 s (no modulated irradiance), a relative standard deviation of the measured irradiance of between **0.001 %** and **0.003 %** was observed, which mainly includes the noises of the photodiode and LIS-A. In the case of the response of the spectroradiometer, these relative standards deviations are around 10 times higher (from **0.012 %** to **0.021 %**). The conclusion is that this variation is dominated by the noise of the spectroradiometer. **Therefore, it can be said that any relative variation of the light source much lower than 0.01 % won't increase significantly the error in the calibration of this instrument.**

The second conclusion that can be drawn consistently from Table 2 is that larger integration times and lower periods favors the increase of the SNR in the response of the spectroradiometer. The larger the ratio integration time / period, the larger the SNR.

It is found in general that the response of the spectroradiometer present is lower than the relative variation of the irradiance, save when the latter is lower than 0.01 %.

In Table 2, the relative standard deviations of the spectroradiometer responses for 580 nm and for the spectrally-integrated value (470 nm – 700 nm) are very similar. It indicates **that the dominant noise of the responses at different wavelengths is correlated, affecting all the wavelengths in the same way. The noise cannot be decreased by spectral integration.** One possible explanation might be in the accuracy in realizing the integration time in each acquisition, that is used internally for calculating the final response of the spectroradiometer. Note that the integration time returned by the spectroradiometer provide only four significant digits, and that when this is irradiated with an irradiance with a stability of 0.01 %, the variation of the internally selected values of integration time is 0.85 %.

These conclusions can be supported theoretically as it follows:

Given a modulation of the irradiance as:

$$E = E_{\max} \frac{[1 - B \cos(2\pi(t - t_0)/P)]}{(1 + B)} \quad (2)$$

where t_0 is initial time, and B is relative amplitude of the irradiance.

The standard deviation of the temporally-integrated response during an integration time t_{int} , can be expressed as:

$$H = \frac{H_{\max}}{(1 + B)} \int_0^{t_{\text{int}}} [1 - B \cos(2\pi(t - t_0)/P)] dt \quad (3)$$

$$H = \frac{H_{\max}}{(1 + B)} \left[t_{\text{int}} - \frac{BP}{2\pi} \sin(2\pi\Delta t/P) \right] \quad (4)$$

with $\Delta t = t_{\text{int}} - t_0$.

The relative deviation of H can be expressed as:

$$\Delta_r H = \frac{H - H(\Delta t = 0)}{H(\Delta t = 0)} = -\frac{BP}{2\pi t_{\text{int}}} \sin(2\pi\Delta t/P) \quad (5)$$

The relative standard deviation of H is obtained as:

$$\sigma_{H,\text{rel}} = \text{std}(\Delta_r H) = \frac{BP}{2\pi t_{\text{int}}} \text{std}[\sin(2\pi\Delta t/P)] \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{H,\text{rel}} = \left(\frac{B}{2\sqrt{2}\pi} \right) \times \left(\frac{P}{t_{\text{int}}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The relative standard deviation of the response of the spectroradiometer (σ_{rel}) would need to add the relative variation due to its noise ($\sigma_{\text{SP,rel}}$), as:

$$\sigma_{\text{rel}} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{SP,rel}}^2 + \sigma_{H,\text{rel}}^2} = \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{SP,rel}}^2 + \left(\frac{B}{2\sqrt{2}\pi} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{P}{t_{\text{int}}} \right)^2} \quad (8)$$

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